

Glaciers Are Alive

A global study reveals overlooked animal diversity in glacier environments – and its growing risk of decline

152
animal species
recorded

14
classes across
7 phyla

73
species are known
only from glacial
habitats

Some glacier
specialists may lose
most or all of their
known habitat by
2100

Understanding glacier fauna is
essential for conservation

Reference: Simoncini et al., 2026. PNAS. 123 (25) e2514455123. 10.1073/pnas.2514455123

Infographic Paper.

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Reference:

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